

Use of Phosphorus Pentoxide. Preparation of Half-esters through Selective Esterification

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Methyl 2-, 3-, 4-carboxyphenylacetate and methyl 2-, 3-, 4-carboxyphenoxyacetate have been prepared through selective esterification of the aliphatic carboxylic acid function of the corresponding dicarboxylic acids using a mixture of phosphorus pentoxide (1 part), anhydrous copper sulphate (5 parts) and anhydrous sodium sulphate (5 parts). All the isomeric half-esters have been prepared through partial hydrolysis of the corresponding dimethylesters.

PHOSPHORUS pentoxide diluted with anhydrous copper sulphate and sodium sulphate exhibited an unusual power for the selective esterification of aliphatic primary carboxylic acids with primary alcohols while aromatic carboxylic acids remained unaffected under the experimental condition¹. With a view to investigating the synthetic potentiality of this fact, the half-esters of several dicarboxylic acids possessing both the aromatic and aliphatic primary carboxylic acids were prepared which revealed that the latter carboxylic group invariably underwent esterification with primary alcohols in the presence of this reagent. Very recently, the use of phosphorus pentoxide during esterification of organic acids has been reported by other workers². A typical experiment consisted of heating under reflux a mixture containing the dicarboxylic acid (0.1 mol), anhydrous alcohol (50 ml) and the reagent (4 g) for 4 h on a steam-bath. On usual workup with a mixture of ether and benzene, the reaction mixture furnished the neutral dicarboxy compound and the half-ester, in 10–20 and 60–70% yields, respectively.

A thorough investigation was carried out selecting 2-carboxyphenoxy acetic acid (1). In the aforementioned method, it furnished the diethyl ester and a half-ester, m.p. 99–100°, in the expected yields. The latter was found to be ethyl 2-carboxyphenoxyacetate (II, R=Et) through its conversion into phenoxyacetic acid. This half ester II (R=Et) was also prepared through the oxidation of ethyl 2-formylphenoxyacetate by bromate in boiling acetic acid³. Moreover, the diethyl ester III (R=Et), obtained from 1, on partial hydrolysis, produced an isomeric half-ester identified as 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (IV, R=Et), m.p. 84°. The assignment of the structures of the half-esters derived from various dicarboxylic acids was based on the analogy of the aforementioned experiments (Scheme 1).

It was envisaged that the carboxy and carbomethoxy groups when attached to either aromatic nucleus or aliphatic sidechain could be distinguished leading to the identification of the half-esters through spectral analysis. The prepared dimethyl and monomethyl esters of 1 through 6 were more useful for ¹H nmr spectral study. In ir, the dicarboxylic acids (1 through 6, nujol) generally absorbed between 1 660 and 1 740, dimethyl esters (7 through 12, film) 1 705 and 1 755, half-esters containing the aromatic carbomethoxy group (13 through 18) 1 60 and 1 45, and half-esters containing the aliphatic carbomethoxy group (19 through 24) 1 670 and 1 755 cm⁻¹; and in uv, generally, the λ_{max} (EtOH) for the aromatic carboxylic acids suffered a hypsochromic shift of about 10 nm with the addition of a drop of aqueous alkali, but the aliphatic carboxylic acids exhibited a slight (ca 3–4 nm) bathochromic shift under similar condition in analogy with the benzoic and phenylacetic acids, respectively. However, the ¹H

Scheme 1

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TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRA

Compd. no.	Aromatic protons	Aliphatic protons CH ₂ - COO - (2H, s)	Carboxy protons COOH	Carbomethoxy protons COOCH ₃ (3H, s)*
1	7.0-8.2 (4H, m)	4.85	11.0 (2H, bs)	
2	6.5-8.0 (4H, m)	4.80	<i>b</i>	
3	6.5-9.5 (6H, m) ^e	4.70		
4	7.3-8.3 (4H, m)	4.10	9.7 (2H, s) ^a	
5	7.5-8.25 (5H, m) ^d	3.75		
6	7.3-8.8 (6H, dd) ^e	3.75		
7	6.8-7.8 (4H, m)	4.65		3.75, 3.85
8	7.05-7.71 (4H, m)	4.67		3.78, 3.88
9	6.90-7.05 (2H, d)	4.70		3.80, 3.90
	8.0-8.15 (2H, d)			
10	7.2-8.05 (4H, m)	4.00		3.70, 3.80
11	7.70-7.90 (4H, m)	<i>f</i>		3.70 ^g , 3.90
12	7.30-7.90 (4H, dd)	<i>f</i>		3.65 ^g , 3.85
13	7.00-8.10 (4H, m)	4.80	10.10 (1H, bs)	4.00
14	7.20-8.00 (4H, m)	4.90	9.00 (1H, s) ^a	4.00
15	6.90-7.05 (2H, d)	4.70	11.00 (1H, bs)	3.90
	8.00-8.10 (2H, d)			
	7.20-7.60,			
16	7.95-8.05 (5H, m) ^a	4.00		3.85
17	7.28-8.08 (4H, m)	3.65	8.75 (1H, s)	3.85
18	7.45-8.35 (5H, dd) ^h	3.72		3.95
19	6.80-8.30 (5H, m) ⁱ	4.80		3.80
20	7.10-7.90 (4H, m)	4.75	10.45 (1H, bs)	3.85
21	6.90-7.05 (2H, d)	4.75	8.70-9.50 (1H, b) ^a	3.80
	8.00-8.15 (2H, d)			
22	7.20-8.30 (4H, m)	4.02	11.45 (1H, s)	3.70
23	7.28-8.08 (4H, m)	<i>f</i>	9.0 (1H, bs)	3.70 ^g
24	7.35-7.55	<i>f</i>		3.75 ^g
	8.10-8.25 (5H, dd) ^j			3.82
Methyl benzoate ^k	7.38-7.98 (5H, m)			
Methyl phenylacetate ^k	7.21 (5H, s)	3.49		3.58

*In dimethyl esters the greater δ values represent aromatic carbomethoxyl group. ^aExchangeable with D₂O. ^bCarboxy proton did not appear. ^c2H's exchangeable with D₂O when (2H, d) at δ 7.0-7.1 and (2H, d) at 7.9-8.0 appeared. ^d(4H, m) appeared. ^eCDCl₃-DMSO-d₆, 2H's exchangeable with D₂O when (4H, dd) appeared at δ 7.5-8.4. ^fMethylene protons merged. ^gCarboxy proton merged. ^hExchangeable with D₂O, when (4H, dd) appeared at δ 7.45-8.35. ⁱExchangeable with D₂O, when (4H, m) appeared at δ 6.80-8.30. ^jChanges to δ 7.30-8.35 (4H, dd) with D₂O. ^kRef. 11.

nmr revealed that the former half-esters (13 through 18) gave singlets due to methyl group at the down-field region (0.1 to 0.25 ppm) compared to the latter half-esters (19 through 24) (Table 1). Thus it became possible to identify each one of the half-esters through the ¹H nmr spectroscopy when the spectra of both the isomers were available.

Experimental

Freshly prepared intimate mixture of anhydrous copper sulphate (100 g), phosphorus pentoxide (20 g) and anhydrous sodium sulphate (100 g) was used as the esterifying agent. Derived compounds were identified through satisfactory analytical data ($\pm$ 0.4% C and H), comparison of the observed boiling or melting points (uncorrected) with the reported values, ir data (Perkin-Elmer 177 infracord spectrophotometer), uv data (Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer), and ¹H nmr data (mostly at 60 MHz in CDCl₃ with Me₄Si, unless otherwise stated, Table 1), tlc, N.E.; 2-, 3- and 4-carboxyphenoxyacetic acids (1, 2 and 3, respectively), 2-, 3- and 4-

carboxyphenylacetic acids (4, 5 and 6, respectively), and 1-carboxycyclohexylacetic acid were prepared by the known methods.

Ethyl 2-carboxyphenoxyacetate (II, R=Et);

Method 1: Bromate oxidation of ethyl 2-formylphenoxyacetate: The reported⁴ 2-formylphenoxyacetic acid was esterified in the usual way with ethanol and concentrated sulphuric acid (20 h reflux) to produce ethyl 2-formylphenoxyacetate as a viscous pale yellow oil (66%), b.p. 175-80°/8 mm; δ 1.2 (3H, t), 4.15 (2H, q), 4.70 (2H, s), 6.7-7.7 (4H, m), 10.5 (1H, s). A mixture of this formyl compound (440 mg), potassium bromate (200 mg), glacial acetic acid (10 ml), acetone (as bromine scavenger, 2.5 ml) and water (5 ml) was heated under reflux (20 min). The reaction mixture on usual workup furnished the acidic part (the desired half-ester; II, R=Et) (50%), m.p. 99-100° (needles from dilute ethanol), N.E. 226 $\pm$ 5, which indicated the presence of both carboxy and carbethoxy groups in the classical tests and spectral analysis;

λ_{max} (EtOH), 232 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.85) and 289 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.5) shifted to 215–220 and 278 nm, respectively, with a drop of alkali; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 260, 1 735 and 1 20 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.3 (3H, t), 4.32 (2H, q), 4.85 (2H, s), 6.9–8.3 (4H, m) and 9.7–10.4 (1H, b, exchangeable with D_2O).

Method 2: Selective esterification of 1: The oxidation of 2-formylphenoxyacetic acid with alkaline permanganate furnished the dicarboxylic acid 1 (80%), m.p. 191°. A mixture of 1 (0.1 mol, ethanol (50 ml) and the reagent (8 g) was heated on a steam-bath for 8 h. On usual workup, the reaction mixture furnished in the neutral fraction ethyl 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetate (III, R = Et) as a pale yellow oil (45%), b.p. 180–82°/6 mm, and in the acidic fraction, the half-ester II (R = Et; 35%), m.p. 99°. The m.m.p. and spectral data established the identity of the compound. Fifty percent reduction of both the reagent and reaction time, as a modification of this method, remarkably lowered the yield of the diethyl ester III (R = Et; 10–15%) and raised the yield of the desired half-ester II (R = Et; 65–70%).

2-Carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (IV, R = Et): A mixture of ethyl 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetate (III, R = Et; obtained by esterification of 1; 2 g), rectified spirit (20 ml), potassium carbonate (2 g) and water (20 ml) was heated on a steam-bath for 5 min, then removed from the steam-bath and stirred for 1 h when the reaction mixture gradually attained room temperature (35°). It was diluted with water (150 ml) and the usual workup with a mixture of ether and benzene separated the unreacted ester. The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the precipitated solid on the usual workup with ether furnished pure 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (IV, R = Et; 1.8 g), m.p. 84° (crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether, b.p. 44–60°), N.E. 226 ± 5 ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 232 and 291 nm (232 and 296 nm, respectively, after the addition of 1 drop of alkali); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 778, 1 760 and 1 690 cm^{-1} [the characteristic sharp band at 3 260 cm^{-1} of the compound II (R = Et) was absent in IV (R = Et)]; δ 1.35 (3H, t), 4.4 (2H, q), 4.75 (2H, s), 6.95–8.1 (4H, m), and 10.3 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O).

Establishment of structures of the half-esters II and IV (R = Et): The dicarboxylic acid 1 (1.0 g) was treated with phosphorus pentachloride and the resultant acid chloride was added to the ice-cold liquor ammonia to furnish the diamide⁶ (0.5 g), m.p. 210°. The half-ester 2 (R = Et) similarly produced the corresponding amide (65%), m.p. 128–29°; ν_{max} (CHCl_3), 3 480, 3 355, 1 745 and 1 650 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.32 (3H, t), 4.40 (2H, q), 4.85 (2H, s), 6.25 (2H, bs, disappears slowly with D_2O) and 6.95–8.5 (4H, m). The amide was subjected to Hofmann reaction followed by diazotisation (the reaction mixture strongly responded to the azo dye test) and treatment with sodium

hypophosphite in the usual way to furnish phenoxyacetic acid, m.p. 94–96°, which was identical in all respect with an authentic sample. By another method the half-ester II (R = Et) furnished the same amide (90%), m.p. 128–129°, which involved the stepwise uses of oxalyl chloride and cold liquor ammonia. The isomeric half-ester IV (R = Et) furnished the corresponding acid chloride (PCl_5 method) which on treatment with cold liquor ammonia yielded isomeric acid amide (60%), m.p. 164–165°, ν_{max} (KBr) 3 410, 1 710, 1 685 and 1 595 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.40 (3H, t), 4.35 (2H, q), 4.60 (2H, s), 5.8–6.0 (1H, b, possible exchange with solvent) and 6.8–8.0 (4H, m). The amide of IV (R = Et) on Hofmann reaction followed by diazotisation of the resultant amine did not respond to the characteristic azo dye test of the aromatic primary amines.

Preparation of the dimethyl esters 7 through 12: The dimethyl esters were prepared by esterifying the decarboxylic acids with methanol in presence of sulphuric acid in the usual way and the neutral fractions obtained therefrom were purified through distillation. The results are reported in the order, name of the ester (compd. no.), yield %, b.p. °C, (compd. no. of the starting dicarboxylic acid): methyl 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetate (7), 85, 164–66/5 mm, (1); methyl 3-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetate (8), 95, 172–73/10 mm, (2); methyl 4-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetate (9), 95, colourless crystals from dilute methanol, m.p. 94°, (3); methyl 2-carbomethoxyphenylacetate (10), 75, 80–82/2–3 mm, (4); methyl 3-carbomethoxyphenylacetate (11), 85, evaporatively distilled at 100–110/12 mm, (5); methyl 4-carbomethoxyphenylacetate (12), 85, 172–175/20 mm, (6).

Preparation of the half-esters 13 through 18. Selective hydrolysis of the aliphatic primary carboxylic ester groups of 7 through 12: The methyl half-esters were prepared following the procedure described under the preparation of 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (IV, R = Et), substituting ethanol by methanol. The results are presented in the order, name of the half-ester (compd. no.), yield %, state, m.p. °C, (crystallisation solvent), N.E. ± 5 , (compd. no. of the starting dimethyl ester): 2-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (13), 80, colourless needles, 108–09 (very dilute methanol), 211 (7); 3-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid (14), 90, colourless, needles, 115 (dilute methanol), 207 (8); 4-carbomethoxyphenoxyacetic acid⁶ (15), 90, colourless needles, 159 (aqueous methanol), 205 (9); 2-carbomethoxyphenylacetic acid⁷ (16), 80, colourless needles, 142–43 (mixture of ether and petroleum ether, 40–60°) 193 (10); 3-carbomethoxyphenylacetic acid (17), 60, colourless flakes, 83–4 (evaporatively distilled at 140°/8 mm, then crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether b.p. 40–60°), 190 (11); 4-carbomethoxyphenylacetic acid⁸ (18) 85, colourless needles, 110 (aqueous methanol), 192 (12).

Preparation of the half-esters 19 through 24. Selective esterification of the aliphatic primary carboxylic acid groups of 1 through 6: A mixture of dicarboxylic acid (0.1 mol), methanol (50 ml) and the reagent (4 g) was heated under reflux at moisture-free condition for 4 h on a steam-bath. On usual workup, the neutral part was separated from the acidic part. The neutral fraction on distillation furnished the dimethyl ester. The results are presented in the order, compd. no. of the dimethyl ester, yield % (compd. no. of the starting dicarboxylic acid): 7, 10–15 (1); 8, 10 (2); 9, 10–15 (3); 10, 20–25 (4); 11, 20–25 (5); 12, 20 (6).

The acidic part (isolated through sodium bicarbonate extraction) was crystallised to furnish the pure desired half-ester. The results are reported in the order, name of the half-ester (compd. no.), yield %, state, m.p. °C (crystallisation solvent, N.E. $\pm$ 5, (compd. no. of the starting material): methyl 2-carboxyphenoxyacetate (19), 65–70, colorless needles, 100–101 (aqueous methanol), 215, (1); methyl 3-carboxyphenoxyacetate (20), 80, colorless needles, 117 (very dilute methanol), 209, (2); methyl 4-carboxyphenoxyacetate (21), 75–80, colorless needles, 174 (aqueous methanol), 209 (3); methyl 2-carboxyphenylacetate⁹ (22), 60–65, colourless flakes, 98 (mixture of ether and petroleum ether b.p. 40–60°), 193, (4); methyl 3-carboxyphenylacetate (23), 65–70, amorphous solid, 92–93, (evaporatively distilled), 189, (5); methyl 4-carboxyphenylacetate (24), 70, colourless flakes, 136 (aqueous methanol), 195, (6).

Experiments with 1-carboxycyclohexylacetic acid: The acid, m.p. 132°, was esterified with methanol and sulphuric acid. The resultant dimethyl ester was evaporatively distilled at 95–100°/10 mm, ν_{max} (film) 1 738 and 1 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.48 (10H, bs), 2.50 (2H, bs), 3.60 (H, s) 3.65 (3H, s). It was hydrolysed with dilute methanolic potassium carbonate in the aforementioned method to furnish the expected 1-carbomethoxycyclohexyl-1-acetic acid¹⁰, m.p. 56–57°, N.E. 198; δ 1.5 (10H, bs), 2.67 (2H, bs), 3.67 (3H, s) and 8.15 (1H, s). When 1-carboxycyclohexylacetic acid was treated with

methanol and the reagent in the usual way, the above dimethyl ester (10%) and impure (two spots in tlc) methyl 1-carboxycyclohexylacetate¹⁰ were obtained. The latter was a viscous oil which furnished the anhydride, m.p. 54°, on attempted purification through evaporative distillation at 120°/15 mm. However, the crude oily half-ester was chromatographed on silica (120 mesh) and the fraction eluted with ether gave methyl 1-carboxycyclohexylacetate as a viscous oil (70%), N.E. 197; δ 1.5 (10H, bs), 2.6 (2H, bs), 3.62 (3H, s) and 8.25 (1H, s).

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